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POLLINATING ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION: ASPECTS OF CITIZEN SCIENCE STRENGTHENED BY THE BEESNESS PROJECT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN A BRAZILIAN PRIVATE INSTITUTION

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Abstract

Citizen science has emerged as a strategy for environmental education¹, being a valuable approach to engage citizens in scientific processes, co-creation², and knowledge appropriation, addressing complex environmental issues. Education plays a crucial role in fostering understanding, appreciation, and protection of the environment³. This study presents an environmental education initiative implemented in a Brazilian primary school (1st to 5th grade) grounded in the BEESNESS project. The initiative has been contributing to a school-wide sustainability education policy, focusing on environmental issues and connecting students with the challenges of nature

conservation. In the first half of 2024, teacher professional development program was carried out by a Brazilian university's academic group, called Espaço Jataí. This program, together with the BEESNESS group actions, enabled each teacher to propose, in collaboration with the class, a project on environmental sciences. By integrating citizen science principles into project-based learning, students explored ecological concepts. Themes connected to the central axis of the BEESNESS project were: the importance of ecosystem services provided by bees, with a focus on plant species relevant to the foraging of native stingless bees; soil conservation challenges and small-scale sustainable agricultural practices, free of pesticides; and addressing the impacts of climate changes and how to deal with them. Student outcomes will be assessed through an online platform developed within the BEESNESS project. In addition, an event titled "Little Scientists for the Planet" will be held at the school. Thus, children will have the opportunity to fostering a social practice of knowledge sharing with their families, giving rise also to a community engagement with those subjects. By promoting a continuous connection with nature, the present initiative may illustrate the transformative

potential of environmental education grounded in academic knowledge production for fostering citizens committed to ecosystem conservation.

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